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PORTFOLIO ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

Education is a life-long process. In education there are many techniques to assess the student. Portfolio is one assessment technique to assess the student. This paper includes meaning of portfolio, meaning of portfolio-assessment, types of portfolio, and advantages of portfolio assessment, disadvantages of portfolio assessment and Stages in the development of portfolio.

Introduction-

A portfolio assessment is the systematic collection of a students work that is created in response to specific and known objectives that are evaluated in relation to the similar criteria. It contains samples of the student's work where it shows growth over time reflecting on the student's work. It shows the student's strengths and weaknesses of his or her own work that is done over the time.

Meaning

A student portfolio is a systematic collection of student work and related material that

depicts a student's activities, accomplishments, and achievements in one or more school subjects. The collection should include evidence of student reflection and self-evaluation, guidelines for selecting the portfolio contents, and criteria for judging the quality of the work. The goal is to help students assemble portfolios that illustrate their talents, represent their writing capabilities, and tell their stories of school achievement... (Venn, 2000, pp. 530-531)

Two Types of Portfolios:

Process and product portfolios represent the two major types of portfolios.

1 Process Portfolio

A **process portfolio** documents the stages of learning and provides a progressive record of student growth. As a *process*-oriented tool, it enables learners to monitor their own learning systematically, reflect on their learning performance, present a coherent account of their achievements and obtain feedback on their learning.

2 .Product Portfolio

A **Product portfolio** demonstrates mastery of a learning task or a set of learning objectives and contains only the best work... As a *product*, it holds the work records and documents a learner has produced during a course or program, and represents an edited collection of their learning achievements.

- Danielson and Abrutyn (1997) identify three major types of portfolios: working portfolios, display portfolios, and assessment portfolios.
- Seely (1996) identifies four types of portfolios: showcase, documentation, evaluation, and process.
- Burke, Fogarty, and Belgrad (1994) discuss three major categories for portfolios: personal, academic, and professional.
- Campbell, Cignetti, Melenyzer, Nettles, and Wyman (1997) elaborate on a working and a presentation portfolio in their discussion of portfolios.
- **Other types of portfolio**
- Learning Portfolios

- Assessment Portfolios
- Marketing Portfolios
- Job Portfolios
- Showcase Portfolios
- Performance Portfolios
- Personal Portfolios
- Proficiency/Competency Portfolios
- Process Portfolios
- Developmental Portfolios
- Hybrid Portfolios

Teachers use process portfolios to help students identify learning goals, document progress over time, and demonstrate learning mastery... In general, teachers prefer to use process portfolios because they are ideal for documenting the stages that students go through as they learn and progress (Venn, 2000, p. 533).

Stages in the development of portfolio

Stages

1 Planning: how you can plan your learning to take account of the important dimensions of your professional learning in your work context.

Practice: the frameworks you can use to chart your own practice and development.

Gathering and selecting evidence: selection of relevant and appropriate evidence.

Reflecting: ways you can reflect critically on your practice and development.

Meaning Of Portfolio Assessment?

Portfolio is a purposeful collection of student work that exhibits the student's ... In this new era of performance assessment related to the monitoring of students'

In program evaluation as in other areas, a picture can be worth a thousand words. As an evaluation tool for community-based programs, we can think of a portfolio as a kind of scrapbook or photo album that records the progress and activities of the program and its participants, and showcases them to interested parties both within and outside of the program. While portfolio assessment has been predominantly used in educational settings to document the progress and achievements of individual children and adolescents, it has the potential to be a valuable tool for program assessment as well.

Many programs do keep such albums, or scrapbooks, and use them informally as a means of conveying their pride in the program, but most do not consider using them in a systematic way as part of their formal program evaluation. However, the concepts and philosophy behind portfolios can apply to community evaluation, where portfolios can provide windows into community practices, procedures, and outcomes, perhaps better than more traditional measures.

Steps in the Portfolio Assessment Process

1. The teacher and the student need to clearly identify the portfolio contents, which are samples of student work, reflections, teacher observations, and conference records.
2. The teacher should develop evaluation procedures for keeping track of the portfolio contents and for grading the portfolio...
3. The teacher needs a plan for holding portfolio conferences, which are formal and informal meetings in which students review their work and discuss their progress. Because they encourage reflective teaching and learning, these conference are an essential part of the portfolio assessment process (Venn, 2000, p. 540).
 - 1 Students know their own weaknesses
 - 2 Individualized instruction
 - 3 Emphasis on the entire learning process rather than just a one-time performance
 - 4 Portfolio not only shows a student's performance, but also his/her efforts

- 5 Students are responsible for their own learning
- 6 Increase students' motivation and self-respect, and satisfaction
- 7 Students compete with themselves, rather than with other students
- 8 Teacher can use portfolios to adjust teaching
- 9 Promoting student self-evaluation, reflection, and critical thinking.
- 10 Measuring performance based on genuine samples of student work.
- 11 Providing flexibility in measuring how students accomplish their learning goals.
- 12 Enabling teachers and students to share the responsibility for setting learning goals and for evaluating progress toward meeting those goals.
- 13 Giving students the opportunity to have extensive input into the learning process.
- 14 Facilitating cooperative learning activities, including peer evaluation and tutoring, cooperative learning groups, and peer conferencing.
- 15 Providing a process for structuring learning in stages.
- 16 Providing opportunities for students and teachers to discuss learning goals and the progress toward those goals in structured and unstructured conferences.

A portfolio assessment is the systematic collection of a students work that is created in response to specific and known objectives that are evaluated in relation to the similar criteria. It contains samples of the student's work where it shows growth over time reflecting on the student's work. It shows the student's strengths and weaknesses of his or her own work that is done over the time.

Disadvantages of Portfolio Assessment

- 1 Requiring extra time to plan an assessment system and conduct the assessment.
- 2 Gathering all of the necessary data and work samples can make portfolios bulky and difficult to manage.

3 Developing a systematic and deliberate management system is difficult, but this step is necessary in order to make portfolios more than a random collection of student work.

4 Scoring portfolios involves the extensive use of subjective evaluation procedures such as rating scales and professional judgment, and this limits reliability.

5 Scheduling individual portfolio conferences is difficulty and the length of each conference may interfere with other instructional activities. (Venn, 2000, p. 538)

Reference website

1 teaching.about.com/od/gloss/g/Portfolio-Assessment.htm

2. (<http://www.morningside.edu/academics/research/assessment/documents/advantagesdisadvantages.pdf>, March 2006)